

SHARIAH COMPLIANT HOTEL BUSINESS IN MALAYSIA

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Abstract

Since past one decade, there has been an increasing focus and demand on Muslim friendly services and Halal products in Malaysia. The revolution of demand on Muslim friendly services also reported has contributed the increasing demand to Muslim traveller to Malaysia. According to the Global Muslim Travel Index (GMTI) 2018, the increasing number of Muslim population around the world, the increasing of disposable income, the awareness of Muslim friendly services are the main contributors to the growing of tourism industry in Malaysia. In responding to this situation, most of the hotel business in Malaysia starts exploring and venturing into Muslim friendly services business called Shariah compliant business. Therefore, this paper explores the current overview of Shariah compliant hotel business in Malaysia. The overview of Shariah compliant practices to the hotel business in Malaysia are investigated based on the available literature and secondary data.

Keywords: Shariah compliant practices, business impact, hotel business, Islamic tourism, Muslim friendly services, Muslim traveller, Malaysia.

INTRODUCTION

In Malaysia, the tourism industry becoming the second income contributor to the country after the manufacturing industry. The industry also expected to become the biggest income contributor to the country in next 10 years (Nor Zafir *et al.*, 2014). In fact, the tourism industry of Malaysia worth RM 36.9 billion for the gross national income (GNI) in 2009 and aiming to achieve RM168 billion by the year of 2020 (Amir *et al.*, 2015). According to Tourism Malaysia (2013), the increasing number of Muslim travellers who prefer to travel to Muslim countries and the

increasing power of spending among Muslims becoming the main contributors to the growing of tourism industry in Malaysia. It is also believe that the current trends in the tourism industry will also boost up the demand for the Islamic hotel services in Malaysia (Samori & Abd Rahman, 2013; Mohd Yusuf & Muhammad, 2013).

Referring to the previous information, it can be explained why the government of Malaysia keen to promotes Islamic tourism as their new tourism product (Che Ahmad *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, the Shariah compliant hotel business is an example of Muslim friendly tourism product offers by Malaysia to cater the increasing demand of Islamic tourism and Muslim friendly tourism (Samori & Abd Rahman, 2013; Battour *et al.*, 2010). It is also important to note that the interest of Muslim tourist's to access into sophisticated Islamic vacation and having Halal dining experience when the travel is keep increasing. Therefore, this paper explores the current overview of Shariah compliant practices to the hotel industry in Malaysia. The overview of Shariah compliant practices to the hotel industry in Malaysia are investigated based several journal articles. It is hoped that this paper will give some useful tips for future research in this area.

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The needs of Muslim during could be developed base on the Islamic pillars and the Article of Iman. In Malaysia, the concept of Shariah compliant practices looks more concerned to assist Muslim travellers to fulfil their religious needs during their travel (Samori & Abd Rahman, 2013). The reality of Shariah compliant hotel business in Malaysia, it can be said that most of the hotels intended to attract the intention of Muslim market. It is also important to highlight that the Shariah compliant hotel business must not put aside the contribution of non-Muslim market in nowadays global business (Nor Zafir *et al.*, 2014; Henderson, 2010). Besides, the issues related to which hotel really practicing the Shariah compliant practices is still debated among scholars and industry players due to the little gap exist to between the operation of Shariah compliant hotel and the normal hotel business (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018).

Another important issue to be discussed further is about the respond and interests from the industry player towards Shariah compliant business. By looking into current situation of Shariah compliant business in Malaysian, is can be said that most of the international hotel brands are not interested to transform their business into Muslim friendly services business. This might cause by

lack of awareness and understanding towards the Shariah compliant business concept (Markham, 2014). Moreover, the policy matter becoming another concern to be highlighted. The study of Ahmad *et al.* (2018) and Nor Zafir *et al.* (2014) found most of the hotel organisations feel not comfortable with the Shariah compliant practices policy made by the local government of Malaysia. In addition, Ahmad *et al.* (2018) and Nor Zafir *et al.* (2014) also found that the uncomfortable feeling among the hotel organisations in Malaysia derived from the uncertainty of the Shariah compliant practices policy in Malaysia.

Referring to above statements, it can be said that the opportunity of providing facilities and activities to cater the Islamic values have come into focus. For instance, most of the hotels in Malaysia nowadays aggressively promoting their Muslim friendly services such as offering Halal foodservice and provides prayer room to their guest to perform prayer (Che Ahmat *et al.*, 2015; Samori & Abd Rahman, 2013). By looking current situation of Shariah compliant business, it is worth to highlight that the Shariah compliant business is moving forward and well accepted by the market. However, the practicing standard of Shariah compliant business is still not clear and need to be emphasised further.

THE CONCEPT OF SHARIAH COMPLIANT HOTEL

Shariah means the totality of Allah's commands which regulate the life of every Muslim. The main objective of the Shariah practices is to ensure the wellbeing of the human, which lies in safeguarding on their faith, lives, intellect, posterity, and wealth in all aspects (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018). As the religious needs is highly concerned by Muslim's travellers, it is the opportunity to the hotel industry to look into Shariah compliant practices (Nor Zafir *et al.*, 2014). Shariah compliant hotel can be defined as a hotel that provides services in accordance to the Islamic principles (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018). While Che Ahmat *et al.* (2015) described the Shariah compliant hotel as a hotel that following the Shariah aspects in their daily business operation.

Talking about the operation, Ahmad *et al.* (2018), Nor Zafir (2015) and Jurattanasan & Jaroenwisan (2014) mentioned that the Shariah compliant hotel is a hotel that provide a prayer mat, Al-Quran, show the direction of Mecca, operates alcoholic and pork free restaurant, and provide different utensils for Muslim guest dining activity. In addition, Nor Zafir *et al.* (2014)

suggests that unmarried couples should not allow to check in the same room. Nor Zafir *et al.* (2014) also mentioned that, hotel should not allow any drug dealing activities within their hotel premises. Besides, it is mentioned by Samori *et al.* (2014) that the Shariah compliant hotel's funding should come with Shariah compliant contracts and the business also are required to pay their zakat.

By looking into above statements, it can be mentioned that the Shariah compliant practices covers the whole aspects of the hotel business operation. It is also believed that the Shariah compliant hotel business contributes certain portion to increasing number of tourist arrival in Malaysia recently.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Shariah compliant hotel business is still at the beginning stage. Afraid of losing profit especially when alcoholic and pork are not allowed to be served or consumed in their hotel establishment can be the main reason why Shariah compliant business is not in direction of the international brand hotels (Jamil, 2014). Another point need to be taken into consideration is about positioning the Shariah compliant business in non-Muslim market. It is not an easy task to positioning religious related services to multicultural market (Mohd Yusuf & Muhammad, 2013).

Moreover, there are a few different principles and requirements found in Shariah compliant practices (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018; Nor Zafir, 2015; Nor Zafir *et al.*, 2014). In other words, the standardisation, and formal guidelines to guide the Shariah compliant hotel business is still not exist at the moment. Besides, it is also fair to highlight that the concept of Shariah compliant hotel business in Malaysia is still uncertain (Che Ahmat *et al.*, 2015). In responding to the current situation Shariah compliant hotel business, it will be a good idea to discuss and develop a standardised policy pertaining to Shariah compliant practices in Malaysia.

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